

Management of multi-product multi-level Green Ring Humanitarian Supply Chain in Iran using Markov chain

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Abstract

New approaches to increase the speed of response are the primary need of humanitarian supply chains. The probabilistic nature of the amount and duration of procurement of items needed in the humanitarian supply chain has led to the presentation of a new model for multi-level, multi-product humanitarian supply chain management in the form of a dynamic, continuous-time homogeneous Markov chain. Orders can be placed at various levels of manufacturers and distributors to meet humanitarian needs quickly. In the dynamic continuous-time homogeneous Markov chain, to approach the reality of the order process, due to different batches for the order, different demand rates, and the duration of demand fulfillment at each level, hyper-exponential random variables are considered instead of exponential. The empirical data obtained from the humanitarian supply chain of the Green Ring in Iran has been used to order sanitary items to prevent the coronavirus and validate the proposed model. The model output determines the number of orders at each level to fully meet the needs of the Green Ring humanitarian supply chain in Iran. Therefore, this model is applicable in natural environments of unpredictable events for quick response so that the model solves in large dimensions in a reasonable time.

Keywords: Humanitarian Supply Chain, Multi-level Supply Chain, Markov Chain, Coronavirus.

1. Introduction

Every year, natural and human disasters such as earthquakes, floods, hurricanes, droughts, landslides, human attacks, and infectious diseases (most recently Coronavirus) affect different parts of the world. These catastrophes cannot stop, but the

severity of the devastation and the damage can be reduced. During the disaster, humanitarian logistics will immediately help the victims as soon as possible. Assistance to the victims is provided using relief forces and allocating necessary resources. The resources include medical equipment, health, food, clothing, housing, etc. There are supply chains for each of these resources.

A classic supply chain includes suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, and customers. In this supply chain, the physical flow of materials is from the upstream (suppliers) to the downstream (customer), and the flow of orders is from the downstream (customer) to the upstream (suppliers). In a natural or human disaster, humanitarian chains are defined as providing the resources needed. Since the scale of these incidents is usually large and is related to saving lives, the rapid response of the humanitarian chain and its management to supply the required resources is very important.

Most researchers consider a four-step approach to include prevention, preparation, response, and reconstruction to crisis management in the supply chain. These steps are the life cycle of a catastrophe. Prevention refers to mechanisms that reduce general vulnerability and are not directly related to logistics operations. Preparation refers to the various processes before an accident occurs, and its primary purpose is to minimize the effects of subsequent crises. The response phase relates to actions immediately after an accident (Natarajarathinam et al., 2009). The goal of the reconstruction phase is to solve the problems of the victims after the accident. It is at this point that the humanitarian supply chain comes into play.

Supply Chain Management includes all the activities connecting suppliers, producers, distributors, and customers so that the goods are produced and distributed at the right price and time with minimum system costs and maximum customer service level (Tuncel and Alpan, 2010). The humanitarian supply chain is a particular type of supply chain whose performance in disasters plays a vital role in facing, controlling, and reducing disasters (Schulz and Heigh, 2009).

Today, the supplier-retailer commercial supply chain seeks to eliminate the various levels of the supply chain to reduce the cost and the cycle time. But, in the humanitarian supply chain, the first goal is to respond quickly to demand, and the next step is to reduce costs. Therefore, to quickly respond to demand, assume that customers' orders are made at different levels of the supply chain, from producer to retailer. So, the classic assumption of the supply chain that the order is transferred from the lower levels to the

top has changed. Due to the probabilistic nature of the customer order process in the supply chain, the order process is considered a dynamic, continuous-time homogeneous Markov chain. All levels of this supply chain are the nodes of the Markov chain. The preparation time of orders is at different levels of the supply chain as a hyper-exponential random variable. Also, the demand entry rate is a hyper-exponential random variable due to the different number of custom batches for the order. So, the problem is closer to the reality of the supply chain. There is no inventory at any of the levels in this supply chain, and the production is done according to the order. These assumptions in commercial supply chains can also reduce the response time to demand.

2. Literature review

Most of the humanitarian supply chain articles discuss the challenges of cooperation and coordination in this field, successful crisis factors for implementation, performance evaluation, and the concept of the humanitarian supply chain and its complexities.

Ergun et al. (2009) describe the main features of disaster supply chains and highlight the specific issues they face when managing them. Blecken et al. (2009) provide a general reference model suitable for the Markov chain process in humanitarian operations. Their model has been used to support humanitarian organizations when designing supply chain processes to support operations and measure efficiency. Thus, this model improves communication and coordination between organizations. Cozzolino et al. (2012) identify the specific stages of the humanitarian procurement process in which the principles of agility and lean are required.

Hamedi et al. (2012) provide a mathematical model for scheduling and routing transportation to provide humanitarian assistance. Gill (2012) describes the main features of the humanitarian procurement operation and compares it to commercial supply chains. Raghavendra et al. (2014) attempt to create a comprehensive model that describes integrated supply chain operations in response to natural disasters. L'Hermitte et al. (2016) examine the logistics environment and supply chain to identify key features and determine whether agility is required in the humanitarian supply chain.

Bealt et al. (2016) examine the barriers and benefits of establishing relationships between humanitarian organizations and logistics service providers to improve humanitarian aid against crisis operations. Makepeace et al. (2017) compare humanitarian logistics and supply chain management perspectives among programs and

logistics/support staff. Jha et al. (2017) study a humanitarian aid chain that includes the supply chain of relief goods and evacuation in a natural disaster. Nikkhoo and Bozorgi-Amiri (2018) examine the coordination of purchase and distribution in a humanitarian aid chain using an information exchange mechanism.

Gutierrez and Mutuc (2018) provide a mathematical model for identifying the optimal location for a temporary or permanent establishment in a particular geographic area in a humanitarian supply chain. Noham and Tzur (2018) offer a new mathematical model that considers practical aspects of network design in the humanitarian supply chain. Zhang et al. (2019) have developed an integrated reliability optimization model for the humanitarian supply chain and examine methods for optimizing the coordination between the flow amount and each unit's reliability. Bull and Sepúlveda (2019) provide vital guidelines for creating a reference model for humanitarian supply chains by identifying the key challenges facing human resource supply chain management.

Muggy and Stamm (2020) present modeling of the behavior of stakeholders when seeking post-crisis assistance. Fathalikhani et al. (2020) developed four mathematical planning models to test the interaction of non-governmental organizations and government policies on the efficiency of donors, non-governmental organizations, and the government.

Giannoccaro and Pontrandolfo (2002) propose a three-stage integrated approach to the integrated management of the Markov chain, including supply, production, and distribution. They present a model based on the Markov decision-making process and learning reinforcement to design re-ordering policies for the supply chain stages. Chiang and Monahan (2005) studied a two-level, two-channel inventory model based on queue models. This model is planned as a two-dimensional Markov chain with storage state space in the manufacturer's warehouse and the retail.

Huang and Iravani (2007) consider a two-echelon capacitated supply chain with two unequal retailers and information sharing and formulate the rationing stock of inventory and production as a Markov process. The state space includes producer and retailer inventory and determines optimal inventory policies. Qiu-fang and Zhi-yong (2007) consider the whole supply chain as a queueing model. In series and over a period, they minimized customer response time and specified value-free times over the supply chain. Scheller-Wolf and Tayur (2009) present a Markovian production-inventory model in which demand is random, and the Markov chain corresponds to inventory levels.

Ahiska and King (2010) study optimal inventory policies for a recyclable product,

and the characteristics of optimal policies are determined using a Markov decision-making process. ElHafsi et al. (2010) present a system involving a producer or supplier that employs several retailers or customers; they formulate the problem as a Markov decision process and determine the optimal policy. Ahiska et al. (2013) model inventory control for an unreliable supply chain as a discrete-time Markov decision process to find optimal ordering decisions. Kaya et al. (2013) consider coordinating production and transfer policies between a retailer and a supplier in a random environment. They model this system as a Markov decision process. Vidalis et al. (2014) model a two-level supply chain as a continuous-time Markov chain. The process state includes the filling phase and the inventory level over time. Razmi et al. (2015) consider a three-level supply chain (supplier, producer, and distributor) as a continuous-time Markov chain. In this supply chain, demand from the customer enters the distributor according to the Poisson process. Then, the production centers and suppliers respond to the customer order with the duration that follows the exponential distribution. A continuous-time Markov model has been used to evaluate the model performance index. They use a continuous review strategy to control distributor and supplier inventory. In this model, the system's behavior is studied in a finite and definite period. In Vidalis et al. (2014), Markov chain behavior studies in the long run.

Sajadieh and Larsen (2015) developed an integrated inventory-production model for a two-stage supply chain. In this model, the rate of production and demand is a random variable, and the whole system is formulated as a discrete Markov process. Shin and Lee (2015) develop inventory management as a Markov decision-making process with uncertainty in preparation and demand, considering various criteria for selecting the supplier and decision-making. Mizgier et al. (2015) proposed a model for calculating the loss distribution from disruptions in a supply chain network. They used generalized semi-Markov processes to simulate the disruptions in each node and the interaction of these disruptions across the network. Lei and MacKenzie (2019) use a Markov chain model and Monte Carlo simulation to evaluate the supply chain risk modeled by the dynamic error tree.

Warsing Jr et al. (2019) use a Markov model to determine the base stock levels for a two-step supply chain with uncertainty in demand and preparation. The pair of retailer-supplier inventory describes the process state. Zheng et al. (2019) developed a decision-making model in a closed-loop supply chain with two recyclers and one producer. They formulate procurement and producer production as a Markov decision problem and

obtain the optimal production and procurement policy.

Perera et al. (2019) use the absorption of Markov chains to model the effects of disruption in supply chain networks. Cech et al. (2019) present a model of a metallurgical supply chain using a Markov process that evaluates resilience using the overall performance of the supply chain as an indicator. Lei et al. (2019) introduce a Markov chain model and Monte Carlo simulation for the numerical assessment of supply chain risk. Fan et al. (2019) consider a two-channel supply chain, including an online store and several independent retail stores, and obtain the equilibrium state probability of on-hand inventory through Markov chain theory. Kappelman and Sinha (2019) present a dynamic food supply chain with multiple suppliers. They develop a Markov decision process that maintains product quality levels throughout the supply chain stages while selecting the optimal combination of suppliers and their process parameters. Mubiru et al. (2019) consider a single-item, three-echelon global supply chain and present a finite-state Markov decision process model in which the states of a Markov chain represent possible demand states.

Hosseini-fard et al. (2020) introduce a new model that integrates a Discrete-Time Markov Chain and a Dynamic Bayesian Network to quantify the ripple effect in the supply chain. Azar et al. (2020) present a mathematical model based on the Markov chain theory to optimize the issue of outsourcing in the supply chain, which reduces the cost of purchasing, outsourcing, and lost demand.

Cech and Lenort (2021) provide a mathematical model based on Markov chains to evaluate the impact of the funds allocated to strengthening the supply chain's resilience relative to its overall performance. Fathi et al. (2021) present a location inventory optimization model for supply chain configuration, which includes two stages. In the first stage, the inventory level of distributors is modeled in the form of a Markov chain. In the second stage, the number and optimal locations of distributors and the assignment of retailers to distributors are determined using a mathematical program.

Meng and Wu (2023) use the Set pair analysis-Markov chain model to predict the future risk status of China's cruise supply chain system. Chhimwal et al. (2023) Markov chain method is used to discover the degree of circularity in analyzing aluminum material flow at different stages of its life cycle in the Indian aluminum supply chain. Wu and Guo (2023) present a closed-loop supply chain switching system model with Markov jump parameters, which uses simulation to validate the model. Yu et al. (2023) provide a model to evaluate and predict the vulnerability of the natural gas supply chain

by considering the dynamics and stochasticity of the natural gas supply chain and then developing it based on the analysis of the pair of sets and the Markov chain. This model is used in China's supply chain of natural gas.

Liu et al. (2023) present a model based on generalized stochastic Petri nets and continuous-time Markov chains to investigate the operational performance of a green closed-loop supply chain in random conditions and then calculate the steady-state probability of the model. Barbosa-Póvoa and Pinto (2023) present a discrete-time Markov chain model and evaluate the expected disruption costs in steady-state probabilities to consider the likelihood of disruption in the supply chain.

Zhang et al. (2024) apply the Markov Decision Process to model decision-making and coordination in the closed-loop supply chain of power batteries. Rathor et al. (2024) present a new hybrid model using hidden Markov models to solve the problem of temporal Threat Recognition in supply chains. Liu and Vakharia (2024) use a new Markov jump system model in modern logistics management, which deals with its complexities and uncertainties.

Kouchaki Tajani et al. (2024) use the Markov chain to address the uncertainty of donor blood supply in the blood supply chain. The development of the Markov Decision Process model to control an automated guided vehicle between automated production cells in a supply chain in Industry 4 has been carried out by Rácz-Szabó et al. (2024).

Mondal et al. (2024) present a new forecasting model for demand forecasting in a supply chain network based on a Markov chain, Dempster-Safer evidence theory, and Shapely value in trapezoidal type 2 fuzzy space.

Saha and Rathore (2024) introduce a semi-stochastic Markov decision process model for the intelligent management of drugs in the hospital supply chain and solve this model with a multi-agent reinforcement learning method. Alhussam et al. (2024) use the hidden Markov model to detect the state of bicycles in the supply chain of bicycle-sharing systems. The proposed method tracks the gradual changes in the bicycle's state.

According to the literature review and research, the following points are contributions of this paper that are not present in any of the documents to our knowledge.

The ordering process in a multi-level, multi-product humanitarian supply chain is a continuous-time homogeneous Markov chain.

The entry rate of demand is a hyperexponential random variable due to the different number of custom batches in each order.

The service time at each level is also a hyper-exponential random variable according to the different batches in each order.

It is possible to order from the customer to each supply chain level except the supplier and from each of the levels to higher levels, except the supplier.

This Markov chain is dynamic according to the choice at each level (producer, supplier, wholesaler, and retailer).

Because the choice of any supplier, manufacturer, wholesaler, and retailer has a specific cost and risk, the choice is made at each level of the supply chain to minimize costs and delivery time. The number of service providers at each level of the supply chain (supplier, manufacturer, wholesaler, and retailer) is determined, and the issue is their selection for allocation and the allocation rate to them. This model aims to minimize the time to respond to demand by determining the percentage of orders allocated and the demand entry rate from each level of the supply chain to each of the high levels in a stable state.

Since unexpected events, most recently in the coronavirus pandemic, production is based on orders for health items, and the need for a quick response to customer demand is felt much more. None of the events in the world in recent decades has been as severe as the Coronavirus due to their severity, geographical extent, and longevity. In the face of this virus, the speed at which supply chains respond to the supply of health items and medical equipment is crucial. Therefore, this new model is presented to achieve high response speed in humanitarian supply chains and to show the applicability of the proposed model; first, an example is solved with actual data in the Green Ring humanitarian supply chain to make medical masks to prevent Coronavirus infection in Iran, and sensitivity analysis is performed on the model parameters. Then, to evaluate the model in solving problems in different dimensions, several examples in various sizes to order health items to prevent Coronavirus infection have been presented. These examples have been solved using the BARON solver of GAMS software. Since large-scale problems are solved in a reasonable time, this model is efficient and practical in the natural environments of unexpected events. Although this paper emphasizes rapid demand response in humanitarian supply chains, the model also applies to commercial supply chains.

This paper continues: Section 3 provides a complete description of the model (objective function and constraints). Section 4 solves the model, performs sensitivity analysis, and presents conclusions and future suggestions in Section 5.

3. The proposed model

The ordering process in a multi-level multi-product humanitarian supply chain is modeled as a dynamic continuous-time homogeneous Markov chain. Ordering a customer can be considered a random process. The process parameter is time. The different states of the ordering process over time include the state that the system is empty of the order, all producers, suppliers, wholesalers, and retailers, which is considered the state space of this random process.

Customer orders in the number of items enter this supply chain according to the Poisson process. Depending on the number of items in each order, the customer order can be assigned to each manufacturer, wholesaler, and retailer with a specific probability. At none of the levels is there a warehouse. In this random process, the conditional probability distribution of any future situation is independent of the previous one and depends only on its current state. Therefore, this random process is a Markov chain. In this Markov chain, it is possible to transfer from one state to another independent of time (or stage), so this Markov chain is homogeneous. The duration of stay in each node is exponentially distributed before going to the next node; therefore, this Markov chain is a continuous-time homogeneous Markov chain.

In this supply chain, the selection is made at each level. Thus, the state of the process at each level is determined by selecting each of the manufacturers, wholesalers, retailers, and suppliers. Customer orders may not be given to some manufacturers, wholesalers, retailers, and suppliers. So, this continuous-time homogeneous Markov chain is dynamic. In this Markov chain, the states are all communicated, and there is only one class of states. Therefore, this Markov chain is an Irreducible Markov chain. The number of possible states for this chain is constrained. Since all states of a constrained Markov chain cannot be transient, since the constrained Irreducible Markov chains have a class, all states will be recurrent. Therefore, this Markov chain is a Recurrent chain. Since the return time to any state is not infinite. So, it is a positive recurrent. This Markov chain has a class, so the period of all states is equal, and this period is equal to one. Therefore, this Markov chain is non-periodic. Markov chains that are non-periodic and positive recurrent are called Ergodic. Thus, this Markov chain is an Ergodic continuous-time homogeneous Markov chain. An Irreducible Ergodic Markov chain has limiting probabilities independent of the initial state and will be

obtained by equilibrium equations.

This model aims to respond quickly to customer demand, the most critical goal in the humanitarian Markov chain. In this model, to get closer to the reality of the supply chain, it is possible to order the customer to each of the levels of the humanitarian supply chain (producer, wholesaler, and retailer). However, to order at each level, the number of items must be within a specified range.

This model assumes that the input of the customer demand is under the Poisson process, which means that the probability of having demand (not items or orders) per unit of time follows the Poisson process. However, the number of items in each customer order is a random variable that accepts positive and integer values less than a specific value with a certain probability. This probability is equal to dividing the entry rate of each order by a certain number of the total entry rate (regardless of the number of orders in each order). This model assumes that the number of customers who order items directly from the manufacturer in each order is equal to or greater than a certain number. Also, the number of items the customer orders directly to the wholesaler must be in a specific range (less than the number of items given to the manufacturer and more than the number of items ordered to the retailer in each order). The number of items in each customer's retail order should be less than that in each wholesale order.

The order entry rate for each level (Markov chain nodes) is a hyper-exponential random variable. The rate of service (preparation) at each level is also a hyper-exponential random variable due to custom items. The sets, parameters, and variables of the model are introduced in the following, and then the objective function and constraints are defined.

Table 1. The indicators and sets.

Indicator	Description
m	Manufacturers (Producers) $m = \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$;
s	Suppliers $s = \{1, 2, \dots, S\}$;
w	Wholesalers $w = \{1, 2, \dots, W\}$;
r	Retailers $r = \{1, 2, \dots, R\}$;
p	Products $p = \{1, 2, \dots, P\}$;
t	Number of customer customizable batches to the manufacturer $t = \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$;
q	Number of customer customizable batches to the wholesaler $q = \{1, 2, \dots, Q\}$;
f	Number of customer customizable batches to the retailer $f = \{1, 2, \dots, F\}$;

Table 2. The parameters and variables.

Parameter	Description
λ_{sp}^s	Exit rate of the supplier s for the product p ;
λ_{mp}^m	Exit rate of the manufacturer m for the product p ;
λ_{rp}^{rc}	Exit rate from the retailer r to the customer for the product p ;
λ_{wp}^{wo}	Exit rate from the wholesaler w in response to the demand for the product p ;
λ_p^c	Demand entry rate to the system for the product p ;
c_p^o	The cost when the system is free of demand (there is no demand) for the product p ;
c_{mp}^m	The cost is as long as the order is in the manufacturer node m for the product p ;
c_{sp}^s	The cost is as long as the order is in the supplier node s for the product p ;
c_{wp}^w	The cost is as long as the order is in the wholesaler node w for the product p ;
c_{rp}^r	The cost is as long as the order is in the retailer node r for the product p ;
Z	The objective function
a_{mtp}^{cm}	Probability of entering demand with the number t from the customer to the manufacturer m for the product p ;
a_{wqp}^{cw}	Probability of entering demand with the number q from the customer to the wholesaler w for the product p ;
a_{rjp}^{cr}	Probability of entering demand with the number f from the customer to the retailer r for the product p ;
a_{rjp}^{rc}	Probability of completed orders with the number f sent from the retailer r to the customer for the product p ;
a_{mst}^{ms}	Probability of entering orders with the number t from the manufacturer m to the supplier s for the product p ;
a_{wmqp}^{wm}	Probability of entering orders with the number q from the wholesaler w to the manufacturer m for the product p ;
a_{rmjp}^{rm}	Probability of entering orders with the number f from the retailer r to the manufacturer m for the product p ;
a_{smtp}^{sm}	Probability of entering orders with the number t from the supplier s to the manufacturer m for the product p ;
a_{rwjp}^{rw}	Probability of entering orders with the number f from the retailer r to the wholesaler w for the product p ;

Table 2 (continued)

a_{mtp}^{mc}	Probability of completed orders with the number t sent from the manufacturer m to the customer for the product p
a_{mwp}^{mw}	Probability of completed orders sent with the number t from the manufacturer m to the wholesaler w for the product p ;
a_{mrp}^{mr}	Probability of completed orders sent with the number t from the manufacturer m to the retailer r for the product p ;
a_{wrp}^{wr}	Probability of completed orders sent with the number q from the wholesaler w to the retailer r for the product p ;
a_{wqp}^{wc}	Probability of completed orders sent with the number q from the wholesaler w to the customer for the product p ;
λ_{mp}^{ms}	Exit rate from the manufacturer m to the suppliers for the product p ;
λ_{wp}^{wm}	Exit rate from the wholesaler w to the manufacturers for the product p ;
λ_{rp}^{rmw}	Exit rate from the retailer r both to the manufacturers and the wholesalers for the product p ;
π_p^0	Percentage of the time when there is no customer order in the long run for the product p ;
π_{mp}^m	Percentage of the time when the order is assigned to the manufacturer m in the long run for the product p ;
π_{sp}^s	Percentage of the time when the order is assigned to the supplier s in the long run for the product p ;
π_{wp}^w	Percentage of the time when the order is assigned to the wholesaler w in the long run for the product p ;
π_{rp}^r	Percentage of the time when the order is assigned to the retailer r in the long run for the product p ;

Objective function

The objective function contains a sum of five expressions. Each expression derives by multiplying the unit time cost of that state in the percentage of the time the process remains in that state in the long term. The length of time the process remains in each state obtain from calculating the limiting probabilities of any state in the Markov chain. The objective function is of cost type; therefore, it should be minimized.

$$\text{Min } Z = \sum_{p=1}^P c_p^0 \pi_p^0 + \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{m=1}^M c_{mp}^m \pi_{mp}^m + \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{s=1}^S c_{sp}^s \pi_{sp}^s + \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{w=1}^W c_{wp}^w \pi_{wp}^w + \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{r=1}^R c_{rp}^r \pi_{rp}^r \quad (1)$$

Constraints

C1. Equilibrium equation for the customer node;

$$\begin{aligned} T \lambda_p^c \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{t=1}^T a_{mtp}^{cm} \pi_p^0 + Q \lambda_p^c \sum_{w=1}^W \sum_{q=1}^Q a_{wqp}^{cw} \pi_p^0 + F \lambda_p^c \sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{f=1}^F a_{rfp}^{cr} \pi_p^0 - T \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{t=1}^T a_{mtp}^{mc} \lambda_{mp}^m \pi_{mp}^m \\ - F \sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{f=1}^F a_{rfp}^{rc} \lambda_{rp}^r \pi_{rp}^r - Q \sum_{w=1}^W \sum_{q=1}^Q a_{wqp}^{wc} \lambda_{wp}^w \pi_{wp}^w = 0 \quad \forall p \in P \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

C2. Equilibrium equation for the manufacturer node;

C10. The sum of the probabilities of entering orders from each wholesaler to the total number of manufacturers must be one.

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{q=1}^Q a_{wmqp}^{wm} = 1 \quad \forall w \in W, \forall p \in P \quad (11)$$

C11. The sum of the probabilities of entering orders from each retailer to the total number of manufacturers and wholesalers must be one.

$$\sum_{f=1}^F \left(\sum_{w=1}^W a_{rwf p}^{rw} + \sum_{m=1}^M a_{rmfp}^{rm} \right) = 1 \quad \forall r \in R, \forall p \in P \quad (12)$$

C12. The sum of the probabilities of entering from the supplier to the total number of manufacturers must be one.

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{t=1}^T a_{smtp}^{sm} = 1 \quad \forall s \in S, \forall p \in P \quad (13)$$

C13. The sum of the probabilities of entering from the manufacturer to the total number of suppliers must be one.

$$\sum_{s=1}^S \sum_{t=1}^T a_{mstp}^{ms} = 1 \quad \forall m \in M, \forall p \in P \quad (14)$$

C14. The sum of the probabilities of entering orders from the manufacturer, wholesaler, and retailer to the customer should be one.

$$\sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{f=1}^F a_{rfp}^{rc} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{t=1}^T a_{mtp}^{mc} + \sum_{w=1}^W \sum_{q=1}^Q a_{wqp}^{wc} = 1 \quad \forall p \in P \quad (15)$$

C15. All model variables must be greater than or equal to zero.

In the following to validate the model, an example with actual data obtained from the Green Ring Humanitarian Supply Chain is solved, and sensitivity analysis is performed on the model parameters. Then several examples in different dimensions are solved to evaluate the applicability of the model in various dimensions of the problem.

4. Results and sensitivity analysis

In COVID-19 disease, which has recently affected almost the entire world, the provision of health items and medical equipment has dramatically increased due to the need to prevent and treat this disease. Therefore, in this part, an example with actual data is presented for mask supply. The Green Ring Humanitarian Supply Chain is a volunteer-driven, non-profit network established in Iran during the COVID-19 pandemic to facilitate the rapid procurement and distribution of essential health-related

items in underserved urban areas. Comprised of community groups, local producers, wholesalers, and retail outlets, the network operates without a formal corporate or governmental structure. Instead, it relies on coordinated efforts between independent benefactors committed to humanitarian relief. Despite the absence of a dedicated website or central entity, the network maintains operational reliability through structured communication channels, documented transaction records, and consistent supplier–retailer relationships. For this study, empirical operational data related to the procurement and distribution of medical masks in Tehran were collected directly from participating entities in the Green Ring network and cross-verified with internal logs and delivery confirmations. This unique grassroots structure offers an authentic and challenging environment in which to evaluate the proposed humanitarian supply chain model under real-world constraints. The information has been obtained from the Green Ring Humanitarian Supply Chain in Iran to provide masks for the southern regions of Tehran. Then, the sensitivity analysis is performed on the parameters of the example. Then, several examples with different dimensions of the small, medium, and large have been solved with this model.

The results show that the model is quick to solve, even on a large scale. These results make this model suitable for use today. The Green Ring humanitarian supply chain has three suppliers, five manufacturers, three wholesalers, and fifteen retailers. The customer can give the order to any manufacturer, wholesaler, or retailer according to the number of items ordered.

The Green Ring Humanitarian Supply Chain suppliers include Mousavi in Karaj, Rahmati in Tehran, and Salehi in Arak. The manufacturers include Nazif production and Iman production in Arak city, Takpoosh production in Tehran city, Nikpooshan production, and Tamiz production in Karaj. Wholesalers include Tavakoli Wholesale in Karaj, Motamed Wholesale in Tehran, and Davoodi Wholesale in Arak. Retailers include fifteen stores in different Tehran regions: five in Region One, three in Region Two, four in Region Three, and three in Region Five. The customer in this supply chain is a humanitarian project to donate five hundred thousand masks to needy people in deprived areas of Tehran. In the following, the sets and parameters are defined, and the problem is modeled in the form of the proposed model and solved using GAMS software.

Defined sets include $m = \{1, 2, \dots, 5\}$, $s = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $w = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $r = \{1, 2, \dots, 15\}$, $t = \{1, 2, \dots, 5\}$,

$q = \{1, 2, \dots, 5\}$, $f = \{1, 2, \dots, 5\}$, and $p = 1$. The cost of the system when there is no demand is 500 ($c_1^0 = 500$). The demand entry rate equals 500,000 per week ($=500000$). The expenses are million Rials and exit rates per week. Table 3 shows the parameters of examples.

Table 3. Exit rate and cost in the Green Ring humanitarian supply chain.

Levels	Names	Cost	Exit rate
Suppliers	Mousavi	300	300000
	Rahmati	250	250000
	Salehi	280	280000
Manufacturers	Nazif	105	70000
	Iman	150	100000
	Takpoosh	142.5	95000
	Nikpooshan	180	120000
	Tamiz	135	90000
Wholesalers	Tavakoli	180	90000
	Motamed	170	85000
	Davoodi	190	95000
Retailers	Store 1	15	5000
	Store 2	10.5	3500
	Store 3	6	2000
	Store 4	4.5	1500
	Store 5	12	4000
	Store 6	11.4	3800
	Store 7	9	3000
	Store 8	5.4	1800
	Store 9	4.5	1500
	Store 10	6	2000
	Store 11	7.5	2500
	Store 12	11.1	3700
	Store 13	5.4	1800
	Store 14	3.6	1200
	Store 15	5.1	1700

This model is programmed in GAMS software version 24.3.1 and solved using Baron Solver. An Intel (R) Core (TM) i7cpu processor computer with 32 GB of memory has been used to run this program. By solving this numerical example, the objective function is $z^* = 64.912$, and the solution time is 1.547 seconds. The results obtained from solving the model are in Table 4. In this table, the allocation rate to each level of this supply chain is obtained in the long run so that the order reaches the customer with the least cost and delivery time.

Table 4. Order rate assigned to each state.

State	π_1^0	π_{11}^m	π_{21}^m	π_{31}^m	π_{41}^m	π_{51}^m	π_{11}^s	π_{21}^s	π_{31}^s
Order rate	0.015	0.232	0.086	0.024	0	0.188	0	0.122	0.079
State	π_{11}^w	π_{21}^w	π_{31}^w	π_{11}^r	π_{21}^r	π_{31}^r	π_{41}^r	π_{51}^r	π_{61}^r
Order rate	0	0.218	0	0	0	0	0.007	0	0
State	π_{71}^r	π_{81}^r	π_{91}^r	π_{101}^r	π_{111}^r	π_{121}^r	π_{131}^r	π_{141}^r	π_{151}^r
Order rate	0	0.007	0.007	0	0	0	0.004	0.008	0.006

In the following, sensitivity analysis has been performed to show the effect of the parameters on the optimal answer and the problem variables. The parameters that we are interested in examining their effect are the cost of the duration of the order in each of the states (the system is empty of the order, suppliers, manufacturers, wholesalers, and retailers) and the rate of exit from each state (suppliers, manufacturers, wholesalers, and retailers). The amount of change of the parameters is shown in Table 5. In this table, the amount of change of each parameter is written. Inside the parentheses, (* 2) indicates that the parameter is doubled, and (* 0.5) means that the parameter is halved. The rest of the parameters are constant.

Table 5. The rate of change of parameters for sensitivity analysis.

Cases	Parameters					
1	$c_1^m (*2)$	$c_2^m (*2)$	$c_3^m (*2)$	$c_1^w (*2)$	$c_2^w (*2)$	$c_1^s (*2)$
	$c_2^s (*2)$	$c_1^r (*2)$	$c_2^r (*2)$	$c_3^r (*2)$	$c_4^r (*2)$	$c_5^r (*2)$
2	$c_1^m (*0.5)$	$c_2^m (*0.5)$	$c_3^m (*0.5)$	$c_1^w (*0.5)$	$c_2^w (*0.5)$	$c_1^s (*0.5)$
	$c_2^s (*0.5)$	$c_1^r (*0.5)$	$c_2^r (*0.5)$	$c_3^r (*0.5)$	$c_4^r (*0.5)$	$c_5^r (*0.5)$
3	$\lambda_1^m (*2)$	$\lambda_2^m (*2)$	$\lambda_3^m (*2)$	$\lambda_1^{wo} (*2)$	$\lambda_2^{wo} (*2)$	$\lambda_1^s (*2)$
	$\lambda_2^s (*2)$	$\lambda_1^{rc} (*2)$	$\lambda_2^{rc} (*2)$	$\lambda_3^{rc} (*2)$	$\lambda_4^{rc} (*2)$	$\lambda_5^{rc} (*2)$
4	$\lambda_1^m (*0.5)$	$\lambda_2^m (*0.5)$	$\lambda_3^m (*0.5)$	$\lambda_1^{wo} (*0.5)$	$\lambda_2^{wo} (*0.5)$	$\lambda_1^s (*0.5)$
	$\lambda_2^s (*0.5)$	$\lambda_1^{rc} (*0.5)$	$\lambda_2^{rc} (*0.5)$	$\lambda_3^{rc} (*0.5)$	$\lambda_4^{rc} (*0.5)$	$\lambda_5^{rc} (*0.5)$

The results obtained from the sensitivity analysis are in Table 6.

Table 6. Sensitivity analysis results.

States	Cases				
	Base	1	2	3	4
π_1^0	0.015	0.033	0.013	0.003	0.052
π_{11}^m	0.232	0	0.26	0.164	0.036

π_{21}^m	0.086	0	0.129	0.115	0
π_{31}^m	0.024	0	0.02	0.144	0
π_{41}^m	0	0.036	0	0	0.024
π_{51}^m	0.188	0.306	0	0.021	0.147
π_{11}^s	0	0	0.188	0.086	0
π_{21}^s	0.122	0	0.126	0.169	0.016
π_{31}^s	0.079	0.248	0	0	0.386
π_{11}^w	0	0	0.122	0.163	0
π_{21}^w	0.218	0	0.138	0.099	0
π_{31}^w	0	0.268	0	0	0.317
π_{11}^r	0	0	0	0.005	0
π_{21}^r	0	0	0	0.003	0
π_{31}^r	0	0	0.025	0.024	0
π_{41}^r	0.007	0	0.028	0	0
π_{51}^r	0	0	0	0.004	0
π_{61}^r	0	0	0	0	0
π_{71}^r	0	0	0	0	0
π_{81}^r	0.004	0.006	0	0	0.004
π_{91}^r	0.007	0.012	0	0	0.006
π_{101}^r	0	0.005	0	0	0
π_{111}^r	0	0.004	0	0	0
π_{121}^r	0	0	0	0	0
π_{131}^r	0.004	0.006	0	0	0.004
π_{141}^r	0.008	0.062	0.019	0	0.008
π_{151}^r	0.006	0.014	0	0	0

Fig. 1a. to Fig. 1d. plot the change in cost and exit rate of suppliers, manufacturers, wholesalers, retailers, and the order allocation rate to better show the sensitivity analysis results.

Fig. 1a. Supplier allocation rate by changing the order allocation cost and demand exit rate.

Fig. 1b. Manufacturer allocation rate by changing the order allocation cost and demand exit rate.

Fig. 1c. Wholesaler allocation rate by changing the order allocation cost and demand exit rate.

Fig. 1d. Retailer allocation rate by changing the order allocation cost and demand exit rate.

As shown in Table 6 and Fig. 1a, when the allocation cost decreases (supplier allocation cost 1, 150 and supplier allocation cost 2, 125), the allocation rate increases to 0.118 and 0.126, and vice versa. When the allocation cost increases (supplier allocation cost 1, 600 and supplier allocation cost 2, 500), the allocation rate decreases. The allocation rate for both suppliers is zero, and no allocation is made to them.

The allocation rate of manufacturers 1 to 3 is zero when the allocation cost is doubled (210, 300, 285, respectively). As the allocation cost halves, the allocation to these three manufacturers increases to 0.26, 0.129, and 0.02, respectively. Also, as the exit rates of these three producers double (140,000, 2,000,000, and 190,000), the

allocation rate to them increases (0.164, 0.115, and 0.144). Similarly, by halving the exit rate, allocation to producers 2 and 3 is not done, and allocation to producer 1 is 0.036, as shown in Table 6 and Fig. 1b.

When assigning orders to wholesalers, as shown in Table 6 and Fig. 1c, they are not allocated when the allocation cost to wholesalers 1 and 2 double. When the allocation cost to them halves, the allocation rate equals 0.122 and 0.138, respectively. Similarly, the allocation to wholesalers 1 and 2, doubling the exit rate, is equal to 0.163 and 0.099, and when the exit rate halves, the assignment to them is not done.

Table 6 and Fig. 1d show that the cost and exit rate change has been done for retailers 1 to 5. With the doubling of the allocation costs (30, 21, 12, 9, and 24), allocating them is impossible. By halving the allocation cost, the allocation to retailers 3 and 4 are done in the amount of 0.025 and 0.028, respectively, and allocation to retailers 1, 2, and 5 is not done. This allocation is done because, despite halving their allocation cost, their allocation cost is high compared to other retailers. When the exit rate is doubled, allocation is made to retailers 1 to 3 and 5, and when the exit rate is halved, allocation is not made to any of the retailers 1 to 5.

As seen in the results above, the higher the allocation cost in each node (suppliers, producers, wholesalers, and retailers), the less order is allocated to that node. Also, the lower the exit rate of each node, the less allocation is made to that node, which is quite logical. The first result reduces the objective function, and the second is to accelerate the delivery time to the customer.

Several problems with small, medium, and large dimensions have been solved according to Tables 7 and 8. The results have been given according to the value of the objective function and the solution time in Table 9.

Table 7. Exit rate and cost for solving problems of different dimension.

Levels	Number in each level	Cost	Exit rate
Suppliers	Supplier 1	4	500000
	Supplier 2	8	700000
	Supplier 3	12	1000000
Manufacturers	Manufacturer 1	10	300000
	Manufacturer 2	15	600000
	Manufacturer 3	20	900000
	Manufacturer 4	30	800000
	Manufacturer 5	35	200000
Wholesalers	Wholesaler 1	37	500000
	Wholesaler 2	31	600000
	Wholesaler 3	42	700000
Retailers	Retailer 1	52	100000
	Retailer 2	58	200000
	Retailer 3	63	300000
	Retailer 4	70	400000
	Retailer 5	73	150000
	Retailer 6	75	50000
	Retailer 7	78	250000
	Retailer 8	80	430000
	Retailer 9	84	280000
	Retailer 10	87	230000
	Retailer 11	93	80000
	Retailer 12	46	120000
	Retailer 13	48	180000
	Retailer 14	44	410000
	Retailer 15	47	30000

Table 8. Different dimensions of problems.

Examples	Number of				Demand entry rate (million)	T	F	Q
	Retailers	Wholesalers	Manufacturers	Suppliers				
Case 1	15	3	5	3	50	5	5	5
Case 2	45	9	15	9	100	10	10	10
Case 3	100	20	30	20	200	15	15	15
Case 4	200	80	70	50	300	20	20	20
Case 5	300	160	120	100	400	30	30	30
Case 6	350	170	150	120	500	40	40	40

Table 9. Solution results.

Examples	The objective function	Solution time (Seconds)
Case 1	2.7	3
Case 2	2.9	35
Case 3	5.67	234
Case 4	9.56	1043
Case 5	13.43	2145
Case 6	18.76	5004

As seen in the results above, the higher the allocation cost in each node (suppliers, producers, wholesalers, and retailers), the less order is allocated to that node. Also, the lower the exit rate of each node, the less allocation is made to that node, which is quite logical. The first result reduces the objective function, and the second is to accelerate the delivery time to the customer.

Several problems with small, medium, and large dimensions have been solved according to Tables 7 and 8. The results have been given according to the value of the objective function and the solution time in Table 9. As seen in Table 9, this model has determined the number of items and the percentage of orders to different levels of the supply chain in a reasonable time, considering the cost and quick response. Therefore, according to the output obtained from the experimental data of the green ring supply chain in Iran and the quick satisfaction of its demand with the output of the model, as well as the results obtained from numerical data in different dimensions, this model is valid and can be used in supply chains, which need a quick response.

5. Conclusion and future research

Demand response speed is a critical issue in the humanitarian supply chain. Considering this topic, the probability nature of the demand, and the time needed to prepare the demand, a model based on the homogeneous continuous-time Markov chain has been presented. The duration of staying in each state in the Markov chain is exponential. However, in the new model presented, the time in each case is considered a super-exponential random variable due to different categories for orders, different demand rates, and the duration of service in each echelon. This Markov chain makes decisions at each level to determine the state. The process state (selection of each supplier, manufacturer, wholesaler, and retailer) is dynamically determined at each level (suppliers, manufacturers, wholesalers, retailers). So, this Markov chain is dynamic. In this supply chain, production is based on order, and no inventory exists. Demand enters the system according to the Poisson process. Also, entering any number of items in each order is a Poisson process. Depending on the order size, the customer can order to each level, except the supplier. At each level of this chain, there are several service providers.

This model aims to minimize the time to respond to demand by selecting at each

level and determining the rate of orders allocated and the demand entry rate from each supply chain level to each of the high levels in a stable state. Therefore, this model is beneficial for humanitarian supply chain managers who need to make quick decisions to determine the amount of order allocated to each level of the supply chain to supply the required items as quickly as possible. Although this model has been proposed for humanitarian supply chain decision-making, it can also be used by commercial supply chain managers to minimize costs and respond quickly to demand.

For evaluating the model's applicability, given that recently, there has been a need for a much faster response to customer demand in the Coronavirus pandemic, an example with actual data is presented for mask supply. The information has been obtained from the Green Ring Humanitarian Supply Chain in Iran to provide masks for the southern regions of Tehran. According to the results obtained from solving the model with data taken from the Green Ring Humanitarian Supply Chain, the order allocation rate to each level of the supply chain was obtained so that the cost and delivery time were minimized. To show the applicability of this model in solving problems with different dimensions, several examples with sizes of small, medium, and large have been solved using GAMS software.

The results obtained from the solution of the model with the data taken from the humanitarian supply chain of Green Ring show the efficiency and applicability of the model in the natural environments of unexpected events if the demand was quickly answered with the output obtained from the solution of the demand model. Several problems of different sizes were designed to test the model's ability to solve problems, all solved in a reasonable time and showed acceptable results. The sensitivity analysis was performed to check the model output's response to the parameter changes. The sensitivity analysis showed the model output's logical response to the parameters' changes.

For future research, it is recommended that quality be considered in the selection of each mode at each level. The capacity constraint can also be considered for each of the states. The constraints of human resource planning can be included in the model. Modeling a multi-level supply chain by considering delivery time limit, quality, production capacity, and human resources in the form of a continuous-time Markov chain can be an interesting research topic for the future. Other solving methods can be used to solve this model in large dimensions, including metaheuristics.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Consent to publish

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

All data, models, and code generated or used during the study are available from the corresponding author by request.

Statements & Declarations

We confirm that this manuscript contains original work that has not been published before, is not under consideration elsewhere, and will not be submitted elsewhere. All authors have reviewed and approved the manuscript and agree to its submission. We understand that the submission may be checked for similarity using originality-checking software.

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